

MYC directly transactivates CR2/CD21, the receptor of the Epstein-Barr virus, enhancing the viral infection of Burkitt lymphoma cells

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SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

Supplementary Figure 1

A

B

C

Supplementary Figure 1. Effect of JQ1 on proliferation and apoptosis of Raji and Jurkat cells. **A** Proliferation of Raji and Jurkat cells treated with JQ1 at the indicated concentrations for up to 72 h, estimated by cell counting. Data represent mean values \pm S.D. (n = 3). **B** Cell cycle distribution of Ramos and Jurkat cells treated for 48 h with JQ1 at the indicated concentrations. Cells were stained with Hoechst analyzed by flow cytometry. Data are mean values \pm SD. (n = 2) **C**. Apoptosis of Raji and Jurkat cells assayed by annexin V binding and measured by flow cytometry. Data represent means values \pm S.D. (n=2). Graphs represent the fraction of positive cells normalized to the value of untreated cells.

Supplementary Figure 2

Supplementary Figure 2. Expression levels of EBV early-lytic genes upon MYC downregulation. Left: Raji cells were transduced with shMYC-containing lentiviral particles and positively selected with puromycin for 72 h. *BZLF1*, *BLLF1* and *BRLF1* expression levels were measured by RT-qPCR. Data represent mean values \pm SD (n = 3). ** $P < 0.01$; *** $P < 0.005$. Right: Raji cells treated with 8 nM TPA for 48 h. *BZLF1*, *BLLF1* and *BRLF1* expression levels were measured by RT-qPCR. Data represent mean values \pm SD (n = 3). *** $P < 0.005$.

Supplementary Figure 3

Supplementary Figure 3. Silencing of *CR2* impairs Raji cell proliferation. **A** Raji cells were transduced with two lentiviral vectors encoding for *CR2* short-hairpin constructs as well as the empty vector (EV). After 48 h puromycin was added (1 μ M final concentration) and the cells were further incubated for 72 h. Cells were then harvested and the indicated proteins analyzed by immunoblot. **B** Proliferation of Raji cells transduced with the indicated lentiviral particles determined by cell counting. Data represent means values \pm S.D (n = 3).

Supplementary Figure 4

Supplementary Figure 4. Expression correlation between mRNA levels of MYC and CR2 in human thymus tumours (TCGA database), normal spleen and whole blood (GTEx database) according to the Gene Expression Profiling Interactive Analysis (<http://gepia.cancer-pku.cn/>). R, Pearson correlation coefficient.

Supplementary Figure 5

Supplementary Figure 5. CD69 staining of mouse splenic B cells. Mature B lymphocytes from the spleens of *Myc^{flox/flox};Max^{flox/+};cd19^{cre/+};Rosa26^{gfp/gfp}* (MycKO, $n=3$) homozygous and *Myc^{flox/+};Max^{flox/+};Cd19^{cre/+};Rosa26^{gfp/gfp}* heterozygous control mice ($n = 3$) were activated with LPS and IL-4 for 48h. GFP⁺ cells (Myc-depleted B lymphocytes) were gated and surface expression of CD69 was analysed by flow cytometry. Absolute numbers of CD69^{hi} are shown, \pm S.D. ($n = 3$). *** $P < 0.005$.

Supplementary Figure 6

A

B

Supplementary Figure 6. Ramos cells proliferation rate does not affect the infection by EBV. **A** Cell proliferation rate of the cells infected at high and low density cultures. Ramos cells were grown until a density of 0.5×10^5 cells/ml (low density) or 2×10^6 cells/ml (high density), infected with EBV (1:1 vol de B95-8 supernatant) and further incubated for 48 h. The cells were then harvested, washed and the total DNA extracted. The cell densities are shown at the left graph and the relative growth rate at the right graph ($n = 5$). **B** The levels of viral genomic DNA were determined by PCR with primers of the EBNA1 gene. Data was normalized to the mean DNA levels of LDH and CR2 genomic DNA. Data represent mean values \pm SD ($n=5$).

Supplementary Figure 7

Supplementary Figure 7. Effect of JQ1 on the rate of EBV infection. A. MYC mRNA levels from Raji cells treated with 1 μ M of JQ1 for 48 h analyzed by RT-qPCR. Data represent mean values \pm S.D. (n = 3). *** $P < 0.005$. B. Levels of the EBV envelope protein gp350/250 in control cells (DMSO) and MYC knock down (JQ1) cells after 2.5 h of EBV infection. The gp350/250 area was normalized to the nuclei area. Data represent mean values \pm S.D. (n = 3) * $P < 0.05$. Right panel: representative field showing the gp350/250 (green) and nuclei stained with Hoechst 33342 (blue).

Supplementary Figure 8

A

B

Supplementary Figure 8. Double immunofluorescence of MYC and gp350/250 in Raji cells upon MYC downregulation using either shMYC lentiviral particles (**A**) or 1 μ M of JQ1 treatment (**B**). Cells were exposed to EBV for 2.5 h and levels of the EBV envelope protein gp350/250 (green) and MYC (fuchsia) were assessed by immunofluorescence. The micrographs show a representative field.

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SUPPLEMENTARY TABLES AND METHODS

Supplementary Table S1. Primers used in PCR. All correspond to human genes. The primers are written in the 5'→3' direction. Sequence of primers corresponding to EBV lytic genes were as reported [4]

Gene	Forward	Reverse	Product Size (bp)	Use
CR2 +481 bp	AGGATTCTGCAGGTGCTCAT	TGCTTGGGAACCAGGTCTTA	196	ChIP
CR2 +141 bp	GGGTTTTCTTGGCTCTCGTC	ATTGCAGTGGTCCCTCAAAG	188	ChIP
CR2 -35 bp	GTGTGCGCTCAGAACTAGCA	CGACGAGAGCCAAGAAAACC	197	ChIP
CR2 -198 bp	AGTGTAGTGGGTTGCGTGGT	GCGGGCCCTTAAATAGTGTC	212	ChIP
CR2 -525 bp	CATGCAGAGAATCTGGGTGA	GTGCCATGCTGTGTTATGCT	246	ChIP
CR2 +2.2 Kb	GGGTGCGGAAACAATGATAC	CAGTGGGAGCCCTCAAATA	243	ChIP
CR2 Exon9	CAAGAAAGAGGCACCTGGAG	CAGCTTTGCAACGAATCTGA	199	ChIP
CR2-Luciferase	GCTTGTCCCACCCTCACC	GTTCCATCTTCCAGCGGATA	221	ChIP
CR2	CCGACACGACTACCAACCTG	GACAATCCTGGAGCAATGGA	115	qPCR
EBNA1	GGTTCAGCCAGAAATTTGA	CTCGCCTGAGGTTGTAAAGG	151	qPCR
LDHA	TCCTGACTCAGGCTCATGGC	AGACAACCGACCGGCAGA	103	qPCR
LMP1	CGCCTAGGTTTTGAGAGCAG	GATGAACACCACCACGATGA	154	qPCR
MYC	TCGGATTCTCTGCTCTCCTC	CCTGCCTCTTTTCCACAGAA	157	qPCR
CDKN1B/p27	CCGGCTAACTCTGAGGACAC	AGAAGAATCGTCGGTTGCAG	120	qPCR
RPS-14	TATCACCGCCCTACACATCA	GGGGTGACATCCTCAATCC	135	qPCR
BLIMP1	CTGAGAGTGCACAGTGGAGA	TGGGTCTTGAGATTGCTGGT	167	qPCR
PAX5	AGACTTGTTACACAGCAGCA	AGATTGGCCTTCATGTCGTC	165	qPCR
IRF4	GTGTGGGAGAACGAGGAGAA	TTGTACGGGTCTGAGATGACC	248	qPCR
BZLF1	AGGCCAGCTAACTGCCTATC	TGATTCTGGGTTATGTCGGA	139	qPCR
BLLF1	TGGCGAGTTTGCCTCCTCAG	CGTCCAGTGTACGATTTCTTGG	228	qPCR
BRLF1	ACACTCCCGGCTGTAAATTC	TGGCTTGAAGACTTTCTGA	108	qPCR

Supplementary Table 2. Antibodies used in this work. IB, immunoblot; FC, flow cytometry, IF, immunofluorescence.

Antigen	Reference and specie	Concentration, Use
MYC	N262, Sc-764, rabbit polyclonal, Santa Cruz	1:1000, IB/1:40, FC
MYC	9402, rabbit polyclonal, Cell Signaling	1:3000, IB
MYC	D84C12, rabbit monoclonal, Cell Signaling	1:200, FC
CR2/CD21	C-20, Sc-7025, goat polyclonal, Santa Cruz	1:1000, IB
CR2/CD21	anti-CD21-APC, ref 558658, Biolegend	1:100, FC
CD23	anti-CD23-PE, ref 553139, Biolgened	1:100, FC
CD69	anti-CD69-bio-APC, ref 553235, Biolegend	1:100, FC
B220	anti-B220-PE-Cy7, ref 103222, Biolegend	1:200, FC
β -Actin	I-19, sc-1616, goat polyclonal, Santa Cruz	1:1000, IB
β -Actin	C-4, Sc-47778, mouse, Santa Cruz	1:3000, IB
Cyclin A2	H-432, Sc-239, rabbit polyclonal, Santa Cruz	1:1000, IB
PARP-1	H-250, Sc-7150, rabbit polyclonal, Santa Cruz	1:1000, IB
CR2/CD21 FITC	Rat SD IgG2b,K, clon 7G6, BD Pharmingen	1:200, FC
CD23 biotin	Rat (LOU/M) IgG2a,K, clon B3B4, BD Pharmingen	1:200, FC
PE Streptavidin	BD Pharmingen	1:400, FC
CD19 APC eFluor780	Rat IgG2a,K, clon eBio1D3 (1D3), BD Pharmingen	1:100, FC
EBV gp350/250	Sc-57724, mouse monoclonal, Santa Cruz	1:50, IF
MYC	E5Q6W, Rabbit monoclonal, Cell Signaling	1:100, IF

Secondary Antibody	Reference and specie	Concentration, Use
Anti-Mouse IRDye®800	LI-COR (926-32212), Donkey Polyclonal	1:10000, IB
Anti-Mouse IRDye®680	LI-COR (926-68072) , Donkey Polyclonal	1:10000, IB
Anti-Rabbit IRDye®800	LI-COR (926-32213) , Donkey Polyclonal	1:10000, IB
Anti-Rabbit IRDye®680	LI-COR (926-68073) , Donkey Polyclonal	1:10000, IB
Anti-Goat IRDye®800	LI-COR (926-32214) , Donkey Polyclonal	1:10000, IB
Anti-Goat IRDye®680	LI-COR (926-68074) , Donkey Polyclonal	1:10000, IB
Anti-Rabbit Alexa-Fluor®647	Life-Technologies (A31573), Donkey	1:250, IF
Anti-Mouse Alexa-Fluor®488	Life-Technologies (A11029), Goat	1:250, IF

Supplementary Table 3. Plasmids used in this work.

Plasmids	Construct	Source
pmaxGFP	GFP gene	Amaxa
pGL3	<i>Firefly</i> sp. luciferase reporter gene with no promoter region	Promega
CR2-Luc	-315bp CR2 promoter in pGL3	[8]
Ebox1Mut-Luc	-315bp CR2 promoter with Ebox1 deletion in pGL3	[8]
Ebox2Mut-Luc	-315bp CR2 promoter with Ebox2 deletion in pGL3	[8]
4Ebox-Luc	<i>Firefly</i> sp. Luciferase reporter gene regulated by 4 E-box sequences	[6]
pRL-null	<i>Renilla</i> sp. luciferase reporter gene regulated by the T7 promoter	Promega
pCMV-VSV-G	VSV-G gene encoding envelope lentiviral protein	Gift from Bob Weinberg, Addgene plasmid #8454 [7]
psPAX2	GAG and POL genes encoding packaging lentiviral proteins	Gift from Didier Trono, Addgene plasmid # 12260.
pCL-Eco	ENV, GAG and POL genes encoding packaging retroviral proteins	Novus NBP2-29540
pLKO.1 control	Empty vector	Sigma- MISSION
pLKO.1 shMYC 1	Short hairpin RNA TRCN0000039640 against human MYC	Sigma- MISSION
pLKO.1 shMYC 2	Short hairpin RNA TRCN0000039642 against human MYC mRNA	Sigma- MISSION
pLKO.1 shCR2 1	Short hairpin RNA TRCN0000057113 against human CR2	Sigma- MISSION
pLKO.1 shCR2 2	Short hairpin RNA TRCN0000057116 against human CR2	Sigma- MISSION
pMX-cMyc-IRES-mOrange2	Retroviral vector carrying human MYC T58A ORF and mOrange2 ORF separated by an IRES sequence	This work
pMX-IRES-mOrange2	Retroviral vector carrying the mOrange2 gene and an IRES sequence	This work
pThy1-Brainbow3.2	Plasmid providing the mOrange2 ORF to generate pMX-cMyc-IRES-mOrange2	Gift from Joshua Sanes, Addgene plasmid # 45179 [2]
MSCV Myc T58A	Plasmid providing the MYC T58A ORF to generate pMX-cMyc-IRES-mOrange2	Gift from Scott Lowe, Addgene plasmid # 18773. [5],
Lv224-MYC	Lentiviral vector expressing MYC-IRES-Cherry-IRES-puromycin resistance gene	Genecopoeia
Lv224	Lentiviral vector expressing Cherry-IRES-puromycin resistance gene	Genecopoeia

SUPPLEMENTARY EXTENDED METHODS

Cell culture and proliferation

Raji, Jurkat, Ramos, K562, KMyCJ, KMER4, Kp27MER and B95-8 were grown in RPMI-1640 (Lonza) and HEK293T in DMEM (Lonza) both supplemented with 10% (v/v) fetal bovine serum (Lonza), 150 µg/mL gentamycin (Lab. Normon) and 2 µg/mL ciprofloxacin. KMER4 and Kp27MER were supplemented with 0.5 µg/mL puromycin and 0.5 mg/mL of G418 (Sigma-Aldrich). Viable cells were counted in hemocytometer with Trypan Blue or in a Guava cell counter (Millipore) with Guava Viacount reagent.

Cell cycle and apoptosis

Cell cycle and Apoptosis were assayed by flow cytometry. For cell cycle, 10⁶ cells were washed once with PBS and resuspended in 5 µg/mL Hoechst (33342 Thermo Fisher Scientific)-containing PBS-EDTA, incubated 30 min at 37°C in the dark and analyzed by flow cytometry. Apoptosis was assayed with the Annexin V-PE apoptosis detection kit (Immunostep). Briefly, cells were washed twice with PBS and resuspended in Annexin V-binding buffer (10mM HEPES/NaOH pH 7.4) containing 2 µL of Annexin V-PE and 2 µL of 7-AAD. After 15 min incubation (protected from light), 250 µL of Annexin V-binding buffer were added and analyzed by flow cytometry.

RNA and DNA extraction and quantification

RNA extraction was performed using TriReagent (Sigma-Aldrich). Reverse transcription was performed using the iScript cDNA Synthesis Kit (Bio-Rad) using 1 µg of total RNA. For the amplification of EBV lytic genes, RNAs were treated with DNase I (Invitrogen) prior to cDNA synthesis in order to avoid amplification of contaminating EBV genomic DNA. Briefly, 5 µg of RNA were treated with 5 U of DNase I (Invitrogen) for 30 min at 37 °C followed by DNase I inactivation by addition of 3 mM EDTA and incubation at 70°C for 10 min. Finally, RNA was cleaned up using RNeasy Mini Kit (Qiagen). Genomic DNA (gDNA) was extracted with Qiagen DNeasy Blood & Tissue kit. qPCRs were performed in a CFX Connect Real-Time PCR Detection System (Bio-Rad) using 2xSYBR Select Master mix (Applied Biosystem). Threshold cycles (Ct) were determined by default at the beginning of DNA amplification in the exponential phase. The mRNA expression of genes of interest was normalized to *RPS14* levels. Primer sequences are detailed in Supplementary Table 1.

Immunoblot

Cells were lysed in 1% NP40 lysis buffer [50 mM Tris-HCl pH 8, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 10 mM NaF, 1% NP40 (v/v), 0.1% SDS; protease (Calbiochem) and phosphatase (Sigma-Aldrich) inhibitors]. Protein extracts were sonicated (10 cycles of 30 seconds in a Bioruptor Plus Sonicator device) and further clarified by centrifugation. Samples were resolved by SDS-PAGE and transferred to a nitrocellulose membrane. Primary and secondary antibodies were diluted in TBS-

T. Signals were recorded with an Odyssey Infrared Imaging Scanner (LiCor Biosciences). Antibodies used are detailed in Supplementary Table 2.

Transfection and luciferase assays

Luciferase vectors of human CR2 promoter [8] were transfected into Raji and K562 cells using the Amaxa Nucleofector Technology with Mirus Ingenio Electroporation solution. A total amount of 2 µg DNA of plasmids were used for each condition and the cell specific pre-set program available for each cell line was used. Alternatively, HEK293T cells were transfected using PEI (Polysciences, Inc). Briefly, PEI and DNA were mixed in serum-free media in a ratio 2.5:1 PEI:DNA (µg). The Dual-Luciferase Reporter Assay System (Promega) was used following manufactures's instructions. The pGL3 (Promega) and *Renilla* luciferase reporter (pRLnull, Promega) were used as controls. Luminescence was measured in a GLOMAX Multidetector system (Promega). Firefly luminescence was normalized against *Renilla* values as control of transfection for each sample. Relative light units (R.L.U.) represent fold change of luminescence relative to the empty vector (control). Plasmids used are detailed in the Supplementary Table 3.

Retroviral constructs

The retroviral expression vectors were constructed by isothermal assembly of linear DNA fragments [3]. The activation-induced cytidine deaminase ORF sequences were removed from the pMXPIE-AID retroviral vector [1] and the resulting backbone was linked to the orange fluorescent protein gene mOrange2 (from plasmid pThy1-Brainbow3.2, Addgene) generating the empty plasmid pMX-IRES-mOrange2. A MYC T58A gene (synthesized by IDT, Coralville, USA, using the human MYC T58A sequence as template from MSCV Myc T58A, Addgene), was linked to pMX-IRES-mOrange2 upstream to the IRES-mOrange2 cassette, generating the plasmid pMX-cMyc-IRES-mOrange2 or the empty vector without MYC, pMX-Cre-IRES-mOrange2. The lentiviral MYC expression vector (Lv224-MYC) contained the MYC-IRES-Cherry-IRES-puromycin resistance ORFs. This construct and the corresponding empty vector (Lv224) were purchased from GeneCopoeia. The above plasmids are described in the Supplementary Table 3.

Lentivirus and retrovirus production and transduction

For lentivirus production, HEK293T cells were transfected using PEI with the lentiviral packaging plasmids and the construct of interest mixed in a ratio of 1:3:4 (µg of VSV-G:psPAX2:construct). Supernatants containing the lentiviral particles were collected 48 and 72 hours after transfection, clarified at 1500 rpm for 10 minute and filtered through a 45 µm pore size filter. Lentiviral particles were precipitated with PEG8000 (15% w:v). For that, filtered supernatants were mixed with PEG8000, incubated for at least 6 hours at 4°C and centrifuged at 1500xg for 30 minutes at 4°C. Lentivirus-containing pellets were resuspended in serum-free media (concentrated 20X) and stored at -80 °C. Raji and Ramos were transduced with a MOI≥3 in serum free media containing 5 µg/mL polybrene for 12 hours. Complete media was added afterwards. 36h post-transduction cells were washed to remove the lentiviral particles and transferred to fresh medium with

puromycin (1 µg/mL), to eliminate most of the uninfected cells. After 36 - 48 h of incubation with puromycin, cells were harvested for RNA and protein analysis. The empty vector pLKO and the short-hairpin lentiviral constructs were from Sigma Mission. The shMYC1 is TRCN0000039640 and shMYC2 is TRCN0000039642. The shCR2#1 is TRCN0000057113 and shCR2#2 is TRCN0000057116. Retroviral supernatants were produced by transient calcium phosphate transfection of NIH-293T cells with pCL-ECO (Imgenex) and pMX-Orange or pMX-MYC-Orange retroviral constructs. The above plasmids are described in the Supplementary Table 3.

Flow cytometry and retroviral infection of mouse primary B cells

Single cell suspensions from spleens were prepared and incubated in NH₄Cl buffer to lyse erythrocytes. Cells were cultured (10⁶ cells/well) in RPMI 1640 medium with 15% FBS, 2-mercaptoethanol, penicillin/streptomycin. Mature B lymphocytes were activated with LPS (20 µg/mL; Sigma-Aldrich) and IL-4 (20 ng/mL, R&D Systems) for 48 hours. Single-cell suspensions were antibody-stained in PBS with 2% FBS. Antibodies used were from BD Pharmingen (anti-CD21, anti-CD23 anti-CD69) and Biolegend (anti-B220). Spleen B lymphocytes were identified as follicular B cells (GFP⁺B220⁺CD23⁺CD21^{int}), marginal zone B cells (GFP⁺B220⁺CD23⁺CD21^{hi}). Mouse primary B cells were purified from spleens of 4 months old C57/BL6 wild type mice by anti-CD43 immunomagnetic depletion (Miltenyi Biotech) and cultured for 24 h in RPMI containing 10% FBS, 25 µg/mL LPS (Sigma), 10 ng/mL IL-4 (Peprotech), 10 mM HEPES (Gibco) and 50 µM 2-mercaptoethanol (Gibco) and transduced with control pMX-Orange or pMX-MYC-Orange retrovirus. CD21 expression was analyzed by flow cytometry in Orange-positive transduced cells 48 h after transduction. The antibodies are described in the Supplementary Table 2.

Chromatin immunoprecipitation

Roughly, 2-3 x 10⁷ cells were fixed with 1% formaldehyde (10 min) in rotation and fixation was blocked with 125 mM Glycine (5 min). Fixed cells were washed twice with PBS and lysed in 1.2 mL of lysis buffer (20 mM Tris HCl pH 8.0; 2 mM EDTA; 0.7% SDS; 1% Triton X-100; 150 mM NaCl), adding protease and phosphatase inhibitor immediately before use. Chromatin was sheared to 1000-500bp fragments using a Bioruptor Plus Sonicator for 10-13 cycles (30 s ON, 30 s OFF) and further clarified at 14000 rpm 4°C. Extracts were diluted 7 times in Dilution Buffer and 2-3 µg of antibody were added and incubated at 4°C overnight in rotation. Afterwards, 30 µl of Dynabeads Protein G (Invitrogen) previously blocked with DNA Salmon Sperm (Invitrogen) were added and incubated for 2 hours at 4°C in rotation. Dynabeads were washed in the indicated order with the following buffers in cycles of 5 minutes: Low Salt Buffer (0.1 % SDS; 1 % Triton X-100; 2 mM EDTA; 20 mM Tris-HCl pH 8; 150 mM NaCl), High Salt Buffer (0.1% SDS; 1% Triton X-100; 2 mM EDTA; 20 mM Tris-HCl pH 8; 500 mM NaCl), LiCl Buffer (0.25 M LiCl; 1% NP 40; 1% Sodium Deoxycholate; 1 mM EDTA; 10 mM Tris-HCl pH 8), and TE Buffer (twice) (10 mM Tris HCl pH 7.5; 1 mM EDTA). Finally, Dynabeads were eluted in 200 µL Elution buffer shaking at 65°C for 30 minutes and des-crosslinked with 6 µL RNase (10 mg/mL) and 12 µL 5 M NaCl shaking at 65°C overnight. Then, 2 µL 0.5 M EDTA, 4 µL 1 M Tris pH 6.5 and 1 µL Proteinase K

(20 mg/mL, Thermo Fisher Scientific) were added and incubated shaking for 3 hours at 45°C. DNA was purified with Qiaquick PCR purification kit (Qiagen). For INPUT DNA, 50 µL of chromatin was spared before dilution.

Immunofluorescence

Slides of Raji cells were obtained using a Cytospin (~5x10⁴ cells centrifuged at 600 rpm, 8 min). Cells were fixed with 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA) for 10 min at room temperature (RT), washed with PBS and incubated with 0.1 M glycine for 15 min to neutralize PFA. Samples were washed 3 times with PBS and blocked with 1% BSA in PBS for 30 min at RT. For the double immunofluorescence, samples were permeabilized 5 min with 0.05% Triton X100 in PBS before blocking. Samples were washed twice with PBS and once with PBS-0.05 % Tween-20 and further incubated with anti-gp350/250 or a mix of anti-gp350/250+anti-MYC primary antibodies (for 2 h, RT). Slides were washed twice with PBS and once with PBS-0.05 % Tween-20 and then incubated with the corresponding secondary antibodies for 1 h RT. Slides were washed twice with PBS and incubated with Hoechst 33342 (Invitrogen) 1:2000 in PBS for 5 min, washed twice with PBS and mounted with ProLong™ Diamond Antifade Mountant media. Images were acquired with a ZEISS AxiolMAGER M1 using the same light intensity and exposure time settings across all samples. ImageJ software was used for analysis and quantification. A threshold for signal intensity of gp350/250 was established and the area above that threshold was quantified for all images. For cell number normalization, the area of Hoechst 33342 signal was used. Antibodies used are detailed in Supplementary Table 2.

EBV production and infection

B95-8 cells were seeded to saturation in 20%FBS-RPMI and were kept in culture without changing or adding media. After 3 weeks, EBV-containing supernatants were collected, filtered with 0.45 µm pore size filter, aliquoted and stored at -80°C. EBV infection was carried out by mixing EBV-containing media with cell suspensions 1:1 (v:v). For short-term infections of Raji cells, EBV were previously precipitated with 10% PEG8000, and resuspended in serum-free media (20X concentrated), aliquoted and stored at -80°C.

Statistical analyses

Significance was determined by two-tailed one-sample T test unless otherwise specified. The Saphiro-Wilk normality test was applied to check normal distributions.

References of Tables and Methods

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